

A TEST CASE ON HUMAN BEHAVIOUR AT WORK

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INTRODUCTION

A span of time over a topic brings to mind, what, otherwise, would have taken an age to find, what is learnt at an enormous expense, and is on the world of management to Commerce. This report is based on such a project, which can be surveyed number of times as the topic is continuous. The report over the project can be summarised or elaborated i.e. it can be projected in the way, it is likened.

The question arises that why do individuals behave as they do in organisational setting? The way an individual behaves is largely a function of this motivation. Motivation in a general theme is used to cover the entire range of needs (interest, drives, goals, hopes and aspirations). The desire to fulfil these complexes is motivation. The word motivation is derived from "motive" which is defined as "An inner state that energises activates or moves and that directs or channels behaviour towards goals". Motivation is an inner driver for certain goal-oriented effort. It is a psychological process internal to individuals. It is only evidence in behaviour and can not be seen otherwise.

The factors behind motivation are several, one of them is money. Money is one of the incentives which is perceived as capable of meeting certain needs of people. People look for money because of its exchange value. People can exchange it for getting certain things, which meet their needs. A certain amount of money can buy the physiological needs of people. The possession of sufficient purchasing power is also instrumental in giving a sense of safety and security to people. Money enables people to go in for health care, education, entertainment and also for certain comforts and luxuries. Money is also a status symbol. A moneyed man commands some esteem, prestige and power. He is respected, feared and even loved. These urges create motivation in individual.

Individuals join organisations as employees for purposes of satisfying their needs represented in money. Money incentives are powerful to attract individuals into organisations and to persuade them to stay. Other things being equal, individuals prefer organisations which offer more monetary incentives like higher salary, good fringe benefits, health, care, subsidized housing, bonus retirement benefits etc. Even otherwise, people seek jobs as a means of livelihood or as means of improving their standards of living. To this extent, money is powerful motivation to induce people to seek employment and to enable them to stay there.

It is assumed that satisfied and happy employees get satisfaction and happiness due to attractive monetary incentives, feel motivated to work with commitment and devotion for high productivity and performance. No doubt, employees may be happy and satisfied with their employment, with the money and other benefits they get and with the easy working conditions. But there is very little evidence that under such conditions, positive motivation will automatically follow. This means that monetary rewards extended to employees unconditionally i.e. without making them contingent on performance do not necessarily generate motivation. Such monetary benefits are regarded as, 'rights' which the employees are entitled to by virtue of their association with the enterprise, and not as incentives for good performance. Satisfaction through monetary incentives does not necessarily lead to effective performance.

In this connection, it is interesting to note that Herzberg in his theory of motivation, regards monetary incentive as a hygiene factor meaning thereby that it prevents dissatisfaction. It is not a motivator for better and effective performance. His hypothesis says that the opposite of job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction are no job satisfaction and no job dissatisfaction and not job dissatisfaction and job satisfaction respectively.

It becomes clear from the foregoing that traditional forms of motivation i.e. higher wages, benefits, working conditions (hygienic factors) fail to act as motivators because employees expect these in the normal course. If they did not have these, it may make them angry but it will not motivate them to do a better job.

OBJECTIVES:

The main aim of this project is to know the behaviour of employees in government sector. The questions, which generally ring in mind, are solved through this project to some extent. The ringing questions are varied as, How do employees behave at work places? What are the factors which influence their attitudes, behaviour and performance? What are their needs, interest and motivations? To what extent do the attitudes, sentiments and aspirations of employees determine their work performance and productivity? What is the function of management on the human aspects of work? These and other related human behavioural issues are considered here in this report.

APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY:

To gather first hand and representative information on psycho-social factors in a government organizational setting, an interviewing programme was launched where by a sample of employees was interviewed on their work attitudes and social sentiments. The interviews revealed the pervasiveness of informal group relations among employees and their influence on their work attitudes and productivity. The existence and operation of informal organisation with its own goals, rules, roles and relationships as an integral part of formal organisation came to light through the programme. The results indicated that human behaviour at work places was the outcome of the interplay of relations, sentiments and activities of employees.

The motto behind the creation of the report is to find out the current tendencies of the government employees the approach, they, make towards the work. The approach is a variable factor; it constantly changes its structures. Hence, one can say that the project is in the continuous form.

The personnel interviewed, belonged to an organization, which mainly dealt with minor irrigation projects. But these persons were subjected to regular transfers to other type of project too. Hence, their varied experiences played a vital role in the shape of answers, when they were interviewed.

It is also tried to know that to the extent the objectives of the organisation is fulfilled. Being a government organization, there is multiplicity of objectives; say clean and competent administration, maintenance of office decorum, preservation of the integrity and sovereignty of the nation, cordial inter-relations, and rapid economic growth coupled with social justice and the like. These multiple objectives reflect the true character of the organisation as a broad based entity guided by several concerns and constraints.

The organisation has got strength of 200 persons. Out of which 150 are of technical cadre. Ten percent sample has been considered as representative for interview so, in to 15 technical and 5 non-technical persons were interviewed. Convenience was the criteria to pickup the sample at random, irrespective of class, category, age, salary, religion, place etc. The person interviewed had a range of class I to IV the age between 26 and 51 putting up a service of 5 to 29 yrs.

Table1. CODIFICATION OF PERSONNEL INTERVIEWED

Cadre	Gazetted				Non-Gazetted			
	Age up to 40 years	Code	Age above 40 years	Code	Age up to 40 years	Code	Age above 40 years	Code
Technical	3	TGY 1 TGY 2 TGY 3	4	TEG 1 TEG 2 TEG 3	4	TNY 1 TNY 2 TNY 3 TNY 4	4	TNE 1 TNE 2 TNE 3 TNE 4
Non-Technical	--	--	--	--	3	NNY 1 NNY 2 NNY 3	2	NNE 1 NNE 2

QUESTIONNAIRE:

As the working of employees depend upon the personnel management too. The questions are sprinkled in relation to personal relation too. The interviewed persons criticized and appreciated as per the case, the persons under whom they were working.

Although standard questionnaire was setup for conducting the interviews, the interviewed persons were made free to answer the questionnaire the way they liked. Hence the answers were raw rough and ascent some where.

During the interview, it was found that there were person who insisted on some statements to be noted down and were obliged so, although those statements were not directly linked to the questions, but topic. Although maximum questions were based for getting the answer in the shape of Yes or No, opinions etc. were sought in descriptive manner to know the feelings appropriately.

The questionnaire for the interview was as follows:

1. What made you to take to his job?
2. Do you like it?
3. Do you face personal problems in performing your duties?
4. Do you think that your talents are fully utilized in this organization?
5. Do you maintain cordial relations with higher authorities, colleagues and subordinates?
6. In your duties, what are the factors, which motivate or inspire you?
7. Does the traditional motivating factors viz., wages, increments viz., motivate you?
8. Are you satisfied with your present emoluments?
9. Please comment on your service conditions?
10. Does the time –to-time Government restrictions affect your personal life?
11. Figure out the freedom enjoyed by you in this atmosphere.
12. How do you feel when your personal matter does not get solved, due to official dam?
13. Do you think that Union/ Federation are the only platform to put forward your needs, demands and problems to management?
14. What are your views over bonus?
15. Does leadership qualities play role in the organization?
16. Please comment on the communication, inexistence in the organisation.
17. Do you feel any difference in comparison to your past official life?
18. What is your frank opinion in respect of your relations vis-a-vis divisional accounts, you have worked with the present divisional accounts and vice-versa
19. What is your suggestions regarding further progress of this organisation?
20. What are your future plans?

Through these activities, the attitude of present government employees, although the sample

consists of a particular organisation was tapped in the form of this report.

The survey was conducted particularly for this conference jointly by Prof. Revati Ramrao Rautrao under the guidance of Dr. Gopal Krishnan G.

ANALYSIS:

These interviews are psychologically analysed, so as to know the tendencies and attitude of government employees. The factors are as follows (as per the questionnaires):

1. The persons have joined the concern because of the wordy need. As there was no other field to join, they joined the organisation.
2. All are satisfied with the job, as statistically, there is no other alternative, they could find.
3. Generally, no personal problem is felt, although they are in numbers, as there are very less chances to get the solutions. Their problems are treated as a matter of routine.
4. Interestingly, the answer for the question is equally divided between yes and no. The 'Yes' persons seem to have got sufficient chances to utilize their talents, due to the considerable officers, they have got. The 'No' answer is due to the frustration cropped up out of circumstances.
5. In general, everyone maintains and likes to maintain cordial and friendly relations in the organisation. Even if there is some obstacle in the maintenance of such relations, they try to avert the obstacle. This clearly shows that in the organisation, the atmosphere is positive. In fact, the answers are frank enough.
6. The common motivating factors are money and few words of appreciation are motivating factors in the performance of duties.
7. Interviews have spoken volumes in respect of Herzberg's hypothesis. Only 10% of employees have spoken otherwise. It shows that as the majority feels that the traditional factors are not at all motivating. One can now say so more authentically.
8. Employees are not at all satisfied with present emoluments. They require more to cope up with current high trend of prices.
9. Service conditions are well commented. The issue mainly dealt with free accommodation, as the rents are exorbitant.
10. On this issue, the employees are almost equally divided. Some feel that the restrictions are necessary for national growth, while others feel that fundamental right of freedom should play a better role.
11. It seems that in the current government offices, employees enjoy full freedom.
12. When personal problem does not get solved officially, employees feel irritated and disgusted and this surely tends to affect the working as the motivation is negatively affected.
13. Most of the persons feel that union is the only way to get justice.
14. Bonus is wanted by all, although, most of them knew that they are not entitled.
15. Maximum employee's leadership qualities play role in the organization.
Presently, the leadership's definition is little bit changed and now everyone feels some sort of prestige, through show business to tell others that they are leaders. Naturally, this clearly means that leaders are imposed, not born.
16. Most of the employees do not want to comment over existing communication in the organisation. Most probably, they do not feel so liberal to criticize the system.
17. It is felt that there is no basic difference between past and present official life. The main difference is in working. The past was well-disciplined and people used to do hard work. The officers in the past were more strict, but liberal. They were used to consider the personal problems even.
18. In general, the relations with the Divisional Accountant are cordial. Every one felt that Divisional Accountant should be more co-operative and he should be a good guide in all accounts and administrative matters.
19. No person was so able to put forward his suggestions regarding the growth of the organisation.
Finally, everyone has different motives regarding future life. Some feel to leave the job and do some private business, while others like to settle the life peacefully with children after the retirement.